

Australian
BioCommons

Bioinformatics training needs in Australia

Australian BioCommons and the [National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative](#) offers national training to uplift the skills of Australian biologists and bioinformaticians. We collaborate to ensure we can offer the best training opportunities in areas that are relevant. It is important for us to hear what training you - the bioscience research community - need so that we can best support your research.

This survey should take less than 10 minutes to complete.

By participating in this survey you agree that your responses will be provided to the Australian BioCommons (hosted by The University of Melbourne) and will be used solely for documenting the broad bioinformatics training needs of the Australian bioscience research community and to inform the design of future training events by Australian BioCommons and their partners. Your responses are anonymous and will be protected against unauthorised access and use. Full Privacy Statement: www.biocommons.org.au/privacy

Bioinformatics training needs in Australia

* **1** Where do you work or study? Eg. Melbourne Bioinformatics, University of Melbourne*

* **2** What is the postcode of your usual place of work? Eg. Parkville is 3010.*

3 What is your employment sector?

- Academia/ Research Institution
- Industry
- Non-Profit Organisation
- Healthcare
- Government
- Other (please specify)

4 What are your main Fields of Research?

Tick all that apply

- Agricultural, Veterinary and Food Sciences
- Biological Sciences
- Biomedical and Clinical sciences
- Health Sciences
- Environmental Sciences
- Chemical Sciences
- Other (please choose from: tinyurl.com/ABS-FoR)

*5) What is your job title?

6) What is your career stage?

- Early
- Mid
- Late

7) How would you describe your level of competency in bioinformatics /computational biology?

- None
- Beginner
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Depends on the tool and analysis

8) What are your preferred modes of learning?

Select one or more options

- In-person instructor-led hands-on workshop
- Online instructor-led hands-on workshop
- Self-paced online learning
- Watching videos
- Live webinars
- Reading research reports / methods
- Working through example datasets and vignettes for packages
- Hacky sessions/ coding clubs or in-person support
- Other (please specify)

9) What is your preferred length of training activity?

Select one or more options

- 1 hour or less
- Half day (3-4hr)
- Whole day

10 What is your preferred frequency of training events?

Select one or more options

- One-offs
- Multiple sessions over consecutive days (intensive)
- Multiple spread out sessions (series)

11 Which of the following platforms / tools do you need to learn how to use?

Tick all that apply

- R
- Python
- Command line / Bash / Unix
- Git / Github
- Workflows / Pipelines (e.g. NextFlow, Snakemake etc)
- Portable software (e.g. containers)
- HPC
- Cloud computing
- Galaxy
- Apollo
- None of the above
- Other (please specify)

*12 This question is about the bioinformatics skills you need to learn (e.g. how to analyse RNAseq data).

List up to ten skills

I need to learn how to

13 Are you confident that your training needs will be met by your local institution?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

14 Please indicate the organisations whose training resources you have previously accessed. These could include a webinar, workshop, help desk, written instructions, or documentation from National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative organisations or elsewhere.

Tick all that apply

- Australian BioCommons
- Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney
- Melbourne Bioinformatics, University of Melbourne
- Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF)
- Monash Genomics and Bioinformatics Platform, Monash University
- Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre
- National Computational Infrastructure (NCI)
- South Australian Genomics Centre (SAGC)
- Menzies - School of Health Research
- COMBINE
- University of Tasmania
- I have not accessed any training resources
- Other organisation (please specify)

15 Any other thoughts or comments you'd like to share?

Thank you for taking the time to share your training needs with us. The results of this survey will be published in the [Australian BioCommons Zenodo Community](#).

[Subscribe](#) to the Australian BioCommons newsletter or follow us on [LinkedIn](#) to find out when the results are available and to hear about [National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative](#) events.